

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ФАНЛАР
АКАДЕМИЯСИ МИНТАҚАВИЙ БЎЛИМИ
ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН
АКАДЕМИЯСИ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

Ахборотнома ОАК Раёсатининг 2016-йил 29-декабрдаги 223/4-сон қарори билан биология, қишлоқ хўжалиги, тарих, иқтисодиёт, филология ва архитектура фанлари бўйича докторлик диссертациялари асосий илмий натижаларини чоп этиш тавсия этилган илмий нашрлар рўйхатига киритилган

2022-6/4

**Вестник Хорезмской академии Маъмуна
Издается с 2006 года**

Хива-2022

Бош муҳаррир:*Абдуллаев Икрам Искандарович, б.ф.д., проф.***Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:***Ҳасанов Шодлик Бекнўлатович, к.ф.н., к.и.х.***Таҳрир хайати:**

<i>Абдуллаев Икрам Искандарович, б.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Рўзметов Бахтияр, и.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Абдуллаев Баҳром Исмоилович, ф-м.ф.д.</i>	<i>Садуллаев Азимбой, ф-м.ф.д., акад.</i>
<i>Абдуллаев Рашид Бабажонович, тиб.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Салаев Санъатбек Комилович, и.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Абдуҳалимов Баҳром Абдурахимович, т.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Сапарбаева Гуландам Машариповна, ф.ф.ф.д.</i>
<i>Агзамова Гулчехра Азизовна, т.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Сапаров Каландар Абдуллаевич, б.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Аимбетов Нагмет Каллиевич, и.ф.д., акад.</i>	<i>Сирожов Ойбек Очилович, с.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Бабаджанов Хушнот, ф.ф.н., проф.</i>	<i>Сотилов Гойипназар, к/х.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Бекчанов Даврон Жуманазарович, к.ф.д.</i>	<i>Тожибаев Комилжон Шаробитдинович, б.ф.д., академик</i>
<i>Буриев Хасан Чутбаевич, б.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Холлиев Аскар Эргашевич, б.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Ганджаева Лола Атаназаровна, б.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Холматов Бахтиёр Рустамович, б.ф.д.</i>
<i>Давлетов Санжар Ражабович, тар.ф.д.</i>	<i>Чўпонов Отаназар Отожонович, ф.ф.д., доц.</i>
<i>Дурдиева Гавҳар Салаевна, арх.ф.д.</i>	<i>Шакарбоев Эркин Бердикулович, б.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Дўсчанов Бахтиёр, тиб.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Эрматова Жамила Исмаиловна, ф.ф.н., доц.</i>
<i>Ибрагимов Бахтиёр Тўлаганович, к.ф.д., акад.</i>	<i>Эшчанов Рузумбой Абдуллаевич, б.ф.д., доц.</i>
<i>Жуманиёзов Зоҳид Отабоевич, ф.ф.н., доц.</i>	<i>Ўразбоев Ғайрат Ўразалиевич, ф-м.ф.д.</i>
<i>Кадирова Шахноза Абдухалиловна, к.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Ўрозбоев Абдулла Дурдиевич, ф.ф.д.</i>
<i>Кутлиев Учқун Отобоевич, ф-м.ф.д.</i>	<i>Ҳажиева Мақсуда Султоновна, фал.ф.д.</i>
<i>Ламерс Жон, к/х.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Ҳасанов Шодлик Бекнўлатович, к.ф.н., к.и.х.</i>
<i>Майкл С. Энжел, б.ф.д., проф.</i>	<i>Худайберганаева Дурдона Сидиқовна, ф.ф.д., проф.</i>
<i>Мирзаев Сирожиддин Зайниевич, ф-м.ф.д., проф.</i>	
<i>Пазилов Абдуваеит б.ф.д., проф.</i>	
<i>Рахимов Раҳим Атажанович, т.ф.д., проф.</i>	
<i>Рашидов Негмурод Элмуродович, б.ф.н., доц.</i>	
<i>Рўзиев Рашид Юсупович, тиб.ф.д., проф.</i>	

Хоразм Маъмун академияси ахборотномаси: илмий журнал.-№6/4 (90), Хоразм Маъмун академияси, 2022 й. – 148 б. – Босма нашрнинг электрон варианты - <http://mamun.uz/uz/page/56>

ISSN 2091-573 X

Муассис: Ўзбекистон Республикаси Фанлар академияси минтақавий бўлими – Хоразм Маъмун академияси

МУНДАРИЖА
ПЕДАГОГИКА ФАНЛАРИ

Absalamov X.U. Dars jarayonida og‘zaki muloqot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish usullari	5
Alibekova R.X. Agrar universitetida rus tilini turli profil bo‘yicha o‘qitishning xususiyatlari	8
Amonov A.T., Bahriyeva N.Z. Filologiya fakultetlarida chet tilini o‘qitishda rolli o‘yin usulidan foydalanish xususiyatlari	10
Aripova G.Sh., Ahmedova A.A. Improving the system for forming the idea of international peace and religious tolerance among youth	14
Ashurova Sh. The advantages of using project method in foreign language teaching	16
Bayanxanova I.F. Linguopragmatic features of proverbs in uzbek, korean and english	18
Babakeldiyeva A.A. Bo‘lajak tarbiyachilarda kreativ faollikni shakllantirish	22
Burxonova G.M. Agrar universitetida rus tilini o‘qitishning samarali texnologiyalari	24
G‘ofurov M.U. Boshlang‘ich ta‘limda fanlararo aloqadorlikning ahamiyati	27
Idiyeva L.I. Til o‘rganish ko‘nikmalarini rivojlantirish va uning nazariy jihatlari	29
Ismatova Yu.N. Ta‘limning yangi kredit-modul tizimida talabning mustaqil ta‘limini tashkil etishning ahamiyati va samaradorligi	32
Ismatullayeva G. Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalar kitobxonligini rivojlantirish	36
Jalilova G.G’. “Flipped classroom” модели асосида гапириш кўникмасини такомиллаштиришга мўлжалланган мобил дастурларнинг аҳамияти	39
Kalandarova S.T. Development of business competence of non-philologist specialty students in foreign language	42
Kamolova Sh.U. Teaching reading and teaching activity in esl classes	44
Mamatova N. By making the younger generation a harmonious human being the importance of pedagogical science in education	47
Matyaqubova N.U. Maktablarda kimyo fanini o‘qitishda pedogogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	49
Muhamadiyev T.U., Farmonov G.X. The review of assessing teaching	51
Muqimov M. Pedagogical techniques, methods and tools used in the development of the world's national landscape	54
Nizomova M.B. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillardagi pedagogikaga oid terminlarning tarjima qilish tamoyillari, muammolar va o‘ziga xos texnologiyalari	57
Nomozova M.A., Poyonova M.A. Characteristics of reflective learning	60
Rahmatova D. XVII-XIX asrlarda Xorazm adabiy muhiti namoyondalaridan Pahlavonquli Ravnaq ijodida izdoshlik	63
Salikhova Z.A. Development of reading competence of students at university	66
Saydalieva G. New trends in foreign language teaching	70
Sirojiddinova Sh.S. Description of legal terms in the integration of education	72
Turakulova S.F. National cultural specificity of phraseological units of the korean language	77
Tursunbekov X.R. Za‘monaviy ta‘lim boshqaruvida singapur ta‘lim tizimining ahamiyati	81
Xamidov M.M. Qishloq xo‘jalik oliy o‘quv yurtlarida kasbiy terminologiyani o‘qitish nazariyasi	84
Xasanov I.T. Jismoniy tarbiya vositalaridan samarali foydalanish salomatlik garovi	86
Xurramov J.O’. Boshlang‘ich sinf ona tili va o‘qish darslarida axborot- resurslari integratsiyasi tizimini rivojlantirish usullari	87
Абсаламова Г.Ш. Мишель Монтен “Тажрибалар” асарида “Инсонпарварлик” тарбиясидаги лексемаларнинг парадигматик таҳлили	91
Акрамова Г.А., Мирзарахимова А.А. Экологические факторы совершенствования информационных технологий в эру цифровизации общества	94
Арипова Н.А. Замонавий педагогикада модул технологияси	96
Жалолов Ш.У. Проблемы и возможности использования словарей при обучении русскому языку в ВУЗах страны	99
Жумаева Н.А. Дехқончилик байрамлари халқимиз тафаккурининг ноёб мўъжизаси	102
Зайнабидинова З.М. К вопросу о возникновении русской школы арабистики на примере научной деятельности И.Ю.Крачковского	105
Исмоилова Д.И. Инглиз тилининг турли хил идеографик луғатларини амалий кўллаш хусусиятлари	108
Каримов Ў.У. Ёш авлод тарбиясига ахборот хуружларининг таъсири	112
Матязова Н.С., Отамурадова А.С. Бошланғич синф ўқувчиларида иждоқорлик қобилиятини шакллантиришда математиканинг ўрни	114

The project work has several stages. Depending on the planned result (poster, drawing, photo exhibition, multimedia presentation), it can take one or more sessions. In addition, students receive exploratory homework assignments. Such tasks involve independent work with additional literature, interviewing classmates, teachers, and parents. Project work in a foreign language has a certain general structure, regardless of the type of project and stage of study and can be represented as follows. Stages of work:

1. Work on the topic of the section (mastery of vocabulary, grammatical patterns, listening and reading texts on the topic, working with video material, etc.).
2. Planning (analysis of the topic and problem, identification of sources of information, selection of criteria for evaluating results).
3. Formation of creative groups (distribution of roles, tasks between members of the group).
4. Research (collection and clarification of information, discussion of alternatives).
5. Design of the project (drawings, posters, diagrams, presentations).
6. Presentation of the project (demonstration of the results of the work. Particular attention is paid to the ability to talk about the joint work and its results in English)
7. Reflection (analysis of project implementation, successes and failures, the reasons for this).

When summing up the results of the work, we try to give all students the opportunity to express their opinions and share their impressions. The brightest, original, meaningful projects are awarded with applause and constructive feedback. Each project deserves approval and praise: work and creativity are invested in it. You should not focus on mistakes, they can be quietly fixed and worked out in subsequent lessons. It should be noted that work on the project is carried out not only within the framework of the lesson. It is part of extracurricular and research work. As a rule, these projects are of a long-term nature, a large number of benefits. Practical experience of using projects shows that this method has positive results:

- Internal cognitive motivation develops, which is confirmed by the increased cognitive interest of students in working on the project.
- Work on the project increases the activity of students of different levels of development and abilities (not only gifted children have become interested in working on the project, but also those who study with difficulty. Participation in the project, even if on the sidelines, increases their self-esteem).
- The creative potential of students of different levels of development develops.
- The general outlook of schoolchildren is expanding and their communicative culture is developing.

There are rules for designing a multimedia presentations are recommended:

Keep the presentation in the same style.

Headings, font size and design elements on all slides must be identical.

Don't put too many objects on a slide.

It is not recommended to use more than three different fonts on one slide.

Use as few colors as possible to make text easier to read.

When creating backgrounds, try to avoid standard textures and "stretching" pictures to cover the entire slide.

Handle sound objects carefully. Their use must be justified.

Use ready-made templates for business presentations and the Blank Slide layout for creative presentations.

When working with a presentation, do not repeat what is written on the slide, comment and decipher the information.

REFERENCES:

1. Polat E. S. Method of projects in foreign language lessons // Foreign languages at school. 2000.
2. Sidenko A.S. Pedagogical workshop: from theory to practice of project-based learning // Innovative projects and programs in education. 2008.
3. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching, 5th edition, Pearson. 2015

UDC 428

LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF PROVERBS IN UZBEK, KOREAN AND ENGLISH

I.F. Bayanxanova, Senior Lecturer, Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Samarkand

Annotatsiya. Maqolada o'zaro munosabat ,murojaat qilish jarayonidagi o'zni tutish va fikr almashuvlar muomala madaniyati tushunchasi haqida fikr yuritilgan. Munosabat, murojaat, muloqot, munozara, mubohasa, muhokama, mulohaza singari tushunchalarning barchasi muayyan millat ,ya'ni o'zbek va koreysning ziynatiga mos bo'lgan ziynatlar haqida bo'lib, u etik va estetik me'yorlar, qoidalar bilan amalga oshirilishiga ko'p ta'riflar berib o'tilgan. Maqolada inson dilini ovlash, unga mehr berish, samimiy tilaklar izhor etish ilinji sharq adabiyotida yoritilgan. Sababi,

dunyoda bir ilm borki, bu adabiyotning bosh mavzusi bo'lib kelgan. Bu insonshunoslikdir. Ushbu ilmning ibtidosi esa inson diliga yo'l izlashdir. Ilmu fan ham, ma'naviy madaniyat va san'at ham shu haqda bosh qotirib kelgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *lingvopragmatika, maqol, paremiopragmatika, nutqiy akt, transaktsiya, propozitsiya, muomala madaniyati, xulq-atvor, odoq-axloq, nutqiy faoliyat, qalbga yo'l, o'zaro tushunish, so'z ko'rki, tarbiya asosi, 한국어 속담, 중의적 표현, 직접적 표현, 동음어, 다의어, 단의어. 의사 소통, 치료 문화, 매너, 품위, 연설 활동, 영혼의 길, 상호 이해, 단어 비전, 교육의 기초.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье обсуждается идея сотрудничества, поведение в процессе подачи заявки и культура общения. Такие понятия, как отношение, просьба, общение, дискуссия, дискуссия, размышление - все это украшения отдельного народа, точнее, узбека и корейца, и существует множество определений его реализации этическими и эстетическими нормами и правилами. В статье описывается стремление человека охотиться за душой человека, заботиться о ней, выражать искренние пожелания в восточной литературе. Причина этого в том, что в мире существует наука, которая была первоочередной темой этой литературы, которая называется - антропология. Суть этих знаний – поиск пути к сердцу человека. И наука, и духовная культура, и искусство обращали внимание на эту тему.*

Ключевые слова: *лингвопрагматика, пословицы, паремипрагматика, речевой акт, транзакция, пропозиция, культура поведения, поведение, этикет, речевая деятельность, путь к душе, взаимопонимание, видение, основы воспитания, 한국어 속담, 중의적 표현, 직접적 표현, 동음어, 다의어, 단의어. 의사 소통, 치료 문화, 매너, 품위, 연설 활동, 영혼의 길, 상호 이해, 단어 비전, 교육의 기초.*

Abstract. *In this given article the cooperation idea, behavior in the application process, and communication culture is discussed. Concepts such as attitude, request, communication, debate, discussion, reflection are all about the ornaments of an individual nation, more precisely, Uzbek and Korean, and there are many definitions of its implementation by ethical and aesthetic norms and rules. The article describes the desire to hunt person a person's soul, to care for it, to express genuine wishes in Eastern literature. The cause of this that there is a science in the world that has been the paramount topic of this literature which is called - anthropology. The essence of this knowledge is the search for the path to the human heart. Either science or spiritual culture, as well as art have been paying their attention to this subject.*

Keywords: *linguopragmatics, proverbs, paremioprgmatics, speech act, transaction, proposition, behavioral culture, behavior, etiquette, speech activity, path to the soul, mutual understanding, vision, upbringing bases, 한국어 속담, 중의적 표현, 직접적 표현, 동음어, 다의어, 단의어. 의사 소통, 치료 문화, 매너, 품위, 연설 활동, 영혼의 길, 상호 이해, 단어 비전, 교육의 기초.*

Introduction. *In world linguistics, the transition from the stage of studying language as a theoretical concept to practical linguistics began in the second half of the twentieth century. At this stage, the concept of language as a natural language differed from artificial language, and its specific features were analyzed in depth when applied in the context of a particular text. We know that in the process of speech, not only language units, words, phrases, fixed expressions and other compounds create active communication, but also extra linguistic factors such as the participants of communication - personality factor, time and space factor, speech maker actions and facial expressions directly affects the process of speech. So, it was concluded that the study of semantic, stylistic and syntactic features of language alone was not enough. As a result, the field of "pragmatics" has found its position in linguistics, having its own goals and objectives. As described by S. Levinson: "Pragmatics is a field that looks at the linguistic structure and studies the grammatical interrelationships between language and context, ... pragmatics is the study of all aspects of hidden meaning that semantic theory does not cover, ... it is appropriate for language users to form sentences and sentences analyzes the ability to choose "[8.9 p.24]. It is clear from these definitions that*

pragmatism has a wide scope; this area includes the analysis of concepts such as dexterity, explication and implication of communication, proposition, intention, presupposition, infertility, speech act, discourse. [1.p.57]

Relevance of the topic. If an integral part of a person's spirituality is the culture of behavior, the concepts of behavior, etiquette, speech activity are at its core. It is natural that the traditions, behavior and way of life, which for centuries have been a symbol of high culture, national and spiritual values, are reflected in the personality of each person. This pamphlet focuses on the Eastern view, the norm of human relations, which is directly related to the Eastern philosophy of life, their role in the formation of personal spirituality.

The deceased President of our country claimed that, " It is inevitable that bringing up a well-educated, intellectually developed generation is the most important condition for sustainable development and modernization of the country" . The attitude undoubtedly stems from the individual's behavioral culture. This is linked to education and upbringing, spirituality and enlightenment, which is a sign of perfection. Only mentally, spiritually and physically healthy generation is the bright future of the country. Just as it is impossible to imagine the flight of a bird without double wings, it is difficult to understand the destiny of man and the future of the country without education and spirituality. [2.p 155-158] Every nation has for centuries left a great spiritual treasure for the next generation. Such priceless wealth is the product of hard work, great life experiences, passed down from generation to generation through proverbs, sayings and various phraseologies, serving the aesthetic enrichment of the nation. The richness of language is measured by the vocabulary richness, the unit of phraseology. Thousands of wonderful proverbs and sayings, as well as phraseologies created by people over the centuries, are passed from generation to generation, and over time, their meaning becomes clearer and clearer.

The experimental part of the article. The use of proverbs in the classroom, especially in practical lessons of a foreign language, imposes a number of difficulties on students, as well as the study of how to use a proverb in their native language in the target foreign language, its inconsistency. In the practical teaching of Korean and English to students, it is important to compare the articles in these languages with the existing articles in Uzbek, as well as to study their specific features. It is well known that every nation has its own beliefs, mentality and unique national characteristics. It will have its own fantastic images, symbols of various portable meanings. We will try to make a comparative analysis of these aspects on the example of Korean, English and Uzbek languages. For example, in English: "After dinner mustard", the translation of this proverb is: "Pepper after a meal." It sounds like this in Korean: 소 잃고 외양간 고친다. Actually, the literal translation of the proverb into Uzbek corresponds to "When the property is lost, the barn will be repaired". Or it is appropriate to interpret it as follows: "After the wedding, the drum", "After the battle, the number of heroes increases." [7.p207]. The meaning of proverbs is equal to the meaning of trying to accomplish something after any past work, and the folklore reflects the national and cultural aspects of the peoples in its oral creation. In the Korean nation, cattle are a symbol of abundance, and it is said that a person begins to repair a damaged barn after losing it.

Analysis of the obtained results. Only a correct assessment of the situation, purposeful approach, objectivity, reasonable, fair attitude and sincere communication can be an integral part of the culture of communication. It can tolerate anything, but it is no coincidence that the inability to tolerate injustice is inherent in the nature of our people. Evaluating someone is actually evaluating yourself. Inappropriate reprimands, insults or hurts a person's heart and upset his mood, affect his psyche. It's hard work, like limiting a broken bowl, to crack a sincere treat. Only the correct recognition and explanation of the successes and failures, the pros and cons, of everything — an event or a person — will eliminate disagreements and conflicts. This means knowing the specific secrets of the culture of communication. It is important to react to whom and how. The wedding, which is the main tradition of the Uzbek people, is of special importance. Due to this, the proverb "Drum after the wedding" is unique to the Uzbek people, and when translating the proverb, the word "drum" can not be literally translated into another language.

After all, the uniqueness of each nation, the integration of its traditions is a bright confirmation of our proof. We will explain our idea through the following proverb. In English: "Speak of angels and they flop their wings." Translation: "If you talk about angels, they will flop their wings". In Korean, they say: "“호랑이도 제 말하면 온다” ." The translation is: "If I call him a tiger, a tiger will come." In the Uzbek language, it is like: “ Hizrni yo'qlasa bo'larkan” or “Bo'rini yo'qlasang , qulog'i ko'rinadi” [3.p512]. The meaning of proverbs is that when something is mentioned or spoken about, it also means that what is said is visible. For this reason, it cannot be denied that in English folk proverbs there are many proverbs expressed in the words "angel" and "satan" in harmony with religious views. The tiger has a worthy place in the social life of the Korean people, and there are many proverbs that mean that a tiger is visible when people talk about it. In most cases, the Uzbek language also has equivalents that correspond to bilingual articles. Conversely, if a person is remembered for fear of not wanting to see anyone, the following proverbs, which immediately describe their appearance, are important in their widespread use in usage. Although the semantic meaning of this proverb is the same, but it is created based on the nationality, customs and traditions of each nation. The English translation of the article "Baggards cannot be chosers" is synonymous with "The poor cannot choose," while the Korean translation is "배고픈놈이찬밥더운밥가리랴." This is in Uzbek: "When the poor is full once, it is equal to their becoming half-rich." [2.p108]. The meaning of these proverbs is that a poor person can only afford to eat when he is hungry. Korean people have been consuming rice porridge as a food for centuries. The fact that a person who is hungry for this dish, which is ingrained in folk culture, eats it despite the hot and cold means that the poor have no choice. In the Uzbek language, the proverb that a poor man is half-rich when he is full once also has a deep meaning, as in the above proverbs. So it is clear that the style of expression in all three language variants of these proverbs is related to the culture of that people, the meaning is the same.

Conclusion. In general, proverbs and sayings, which are among the examples of folklore, serve the positive formation of a wide audience, both morally and educationally-aesthetically. This means that the disease is transmitted from the mind to the body. We pay more attention to healing the body. That is why we will not have a place we have not visited, a doctor we have not met, a medicine we have not taken, a doctor we have not seen. We fill our body with various chemicals. True, the cause of the drug can be cured for some time and prevent the disease. But unless the psyche is cured, the body will not be fully healed. Human life consists of the unity of body, soul and spirit. If they are not healthy, there is no perfection. The sign of perfection is based on mental and physical strength. Influencing and treating the human psyche through words and speech is a test case. While there are forces in the human body that are prone to disease, there is no denying that there are immunity and instincts against it. The word breaks, the word corrects. Applause is in words, and curses are in words. Peace is with him, and prosperity is with him. The word kills, the word laughs. Both constructive ideas and destructive ideas are with him. These definitions of the word are not uttered in vain.

REFERENCES:

1. Sh.Safarov. Pragmalingvistika. Toshkent, 2008. 57-bet
2. O'zbek xalq maqollari. Toshkent, 1989, 108-b.
3. O'zbek xalq maqollari, 2012. 512-bet
4. Young H.Yoo.Wisdom of the Far East.1972
5. Yule G. Pragmatics. – Oxford Univ. Press, 1996. 25p
6. Karamatova K.M. Proverbs-maqollar-пословицы. –Т.:Mehnat, 2000, -400 b.
7. Chong Jong Jin. Koreys maqollari lug'ati. –Seul:Tehaksa, 2006, -207 b.
8. Kim Chun Sig. Koreys tili grammatikasi. –Toshkent:KOICA, 2007, -175 b.
9. Kim Jong Suk, Pak Dong Ho. Koreys tili grammatikasi. 1 qism. –Seul, 2005, -570 b.
10. Kang Bong Kyu. Traditional Korean lifestyles. –Seul, 1995, -219 b.
11. 김부식의 삼국사기.1145
12. 김일연의 삼국유.1281
13. 성현의 용재총화.15세기
14. 한국속담집.1996

**ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ ФАНЛАР АКАДЕМИЯСИ
МИНТАҚАВИЙ БЎЛИМИ
ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ**

**ХОРАЗМ МАЪМУН АКАДЕМИЯСИ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**№6/4 (90)
2022 й., июнь**

Ўзбекча матн муҳаррири:
Русча матн муҳаррири:
Инглизча матн муҳаррири:
Мусахҳих:
Техник муҳаррир:

Рўзметов Дилшод
Ҳасанов Шодлик
Мадаминов Руслан, Ламерс Жон
Ўрозбоев Абдулла
Шомуродов Журъат

“Хоразм Маъмун академияси ахборотномаси” Ўзбекистон Матбуот ва ахборот агентлиги Хоразм вилоят бошқармасида рўйхатдан ўтган. Гувоҳнома № 13-023

Теришга берилди: 06.06.2022
Босишга рухсат этилди: 14.06.2022.
Қоғоз бичими: 60x84 1/8. Адади 70.
Ҳажми 9 б.т. Буюртма: № 6-Т

Хоразм Маъмун академияси ноширлик бўлими
220900, Хива, Марказ-1
Тел/факс: (0 362) 226-20-28
E-mail: mamun-axborotnoma@academy.uz
xma_axborotnomasi@mail.ru

(+998) 97-458-28-18